

at each temperature studied. Values for log K_1 and β_1 were found out from the intercepts and slopes of the plots. The recalculated values of log K_1 and β_1 along with the value of log K_1 reported by Pinching & Bates have been shown in Table 1 from 0° to 50°.

TABLE-1

Temp. (°C)	-log K_1 (Bates)	-log K_1 (author's)	β_1
0	4.2845	4.282	0.424
5	4.2631	4.262	0.366
10	4.2449	4.244	0.371
15	4.2316	4.230	0.379
20	4.2176	4.215	0.418
25	4.2066	4.206	0.396
30	4.1980	4.196	0.407
35	4.1914	4.191	0.363
40	4.1878	4.189	0.361
45	4.1869	4.187	0.356
50	4.1863	4.186	0.359

From Table 1, it is clear that the recalculated values of log K_1 are in excellent agreement with those reported by Pinching & Bates, and are represented by his equation,

$$pK_1 = 1206.25/T - 3.3266 + 0.011697 T \quad \dots (9)$$

over the temperature range 0° to 50°. The method adopted in the present recalculation based on modified Davies equation is much simple.

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Thermodynamical Functions of Pyrocatechol Violet Complexes with Bivalent Transition Metal Ions

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3,3',4'-trihydroxy fuchson-2''-sulfonic acid (popular name, pyrocatechol violet), has been extensively used as an indicator and also as a reagent for spectrophotometric determination of a large number of metal ions but views

regarding the nature and number of species¹⁻⁶ in solution are not alike (For brevity the Pyrocatechol Violet would be written PV throughout the text). This note reports, the thermodynamic stability constant, ΔH , ΔS and ΔG for the interaction of PV with bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn ions.

Experimental set-up, instruments and reagents used, systems prepared, etc. were same as in earlier studies⁷.

The accuracy for pK -values reported in Table 1 is ± 0.02 log units and the accuracy of log K values given in Table 2 is ± 0.3 log units. Therefore the precision of ΔH and ΔS are ± 0.5 K cal mole⁻¹ and ± 2 cal mole⁻¹ degree⁻¹. The dissociation

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF PV IN 1.0, 0.50, 0.25 AND 0.10M, KNO₃ AT 25, 35 AND 45°C

Temp. °C	Ionic Strength	pK_1^*	pK_2^*	pK_3
25	0.10M	7.77	9.75	11.71
	0.25M	7.73	9.72	11.63
	0.50M	7.71	9.66	11.60
	1.00M	7.69	9.61	11.55
35	0.10M	7.75	9.72	11.68
	0.25M	7.72	9.70	11.60
	0.50M	7.70	9.65	11.57
	1.00M	7.66	9.60	11.48
45	0.10M	7.71	9.64	11.58
	0.25M	7.68	9.58	11.50
	0.50M	7.65	9.55	11.48
	1.00M	7.60	9.48	11.32

$pK_1 = 0.26$ (literature value).

* Dissociation constants of the two hydroxy proton which get coordinated to the metal.

constants : pK_1 (SO₃H), pK_2 (phenolic OH), pK_3 (second phenolic OH) and pK_4 (phenolic OH, ortho to carbonyl group) for the PV, given in Table 1 are in good agreement with the reported values⁸⁻¹⁰. Table 2 summarises the values of log K at 25, 35

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMICAL STABILITY CONSTANT (log K), ΔG , ΔH (K cal/mole) AND ΔS (IN cal.mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹) VALUES AT 25, 35, 45°C FOR 1 : 1 METAL COMPLEXES OF PV

Thermo-dynamic Parameters	Temp. °C	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)
Log K	25	7.34	8.08	9.23	10.45	15.92	11.71
	35	7.31	8.02	9.13	10.35	15.77	11.59
	45	7.28	7.95	9.08	10.24	15.61	11.47
- ΔG	25	10.90	11.01	12.58	14.25	21.70	15.96
	35	10.30	11.30	12.86	14.58	22.22	15.33
	45	10.59	11.56	13.14	14.90	22.71	16.69
- ΔH		1.90	2.81	4.33	4.55	6.71	5.20
	ΔS	29.21	27.51	27.68	32.55	50.81	36.12

and 45° for 1 : 1 metal ligand complexes along with the values of ΔH and ΔS . The stability of the complexes is mainly due to ΔS values which are

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large and positive though the ΔH terms also make some contribution. The reported values of ΔH and ΔS indicate the involvement of two phenolic oxygen atom in coordination¹¹. The values of $\log K_1$ for the Cu(II)¹², Ni(II)¹³ and Zn(II)¹⁴ complexes of catechol are 14.10, 8.36 and 12.26 respectively which are nearer to the values for the PV complexes of these metals. This also supports the coordination of PV through two phenolic groups.

The colour and $\lambda_{\max}$ of the PV is pH dependent. Below pH=7.0 it gives a maxima at 590 nm. At pH 7.5 two maxima at 443 and 590 nm and at pH $\approx$ 8.0, only one maxima at 500 nm was observed. In the pH range 9.5-10.0, there is no maxima, however, a flat maxima at 460 nm is observed. The mixture containing metal and dye in the ratio of 1 : 1 gave the maxima at 609 nm in the pH range 8.5-9.0 for Mn(II), 580 nm in the pH range 8.2-8.7 for Fe(II), 600 nm in the pH range 7.5-8.3 for Co(II), 590 nm in the pH range 7.0-7.65 for Ni(II), 598 nm in the pH range 5.5-6.5 for Cu(II) and at 598 nm in the pH range 6.7-7.3 for Zn(II). The absorbance of the complexes remain almost constant in the pH ranges given for their formation and the values of $\bar{n}=1$ in these pH ranges indicate the complete formation of 1 : 1 complex. This combining ratio was further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation.

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Solid Reflectance Spectral Studies on Some Uranium(V) Compounds

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SSELBIN and coworkers have reported UCl_5 complexes with ligands containing N, P, As, Bi, O, S, Se and Te as donor atoms.¹ Paul and coworkers have also characterised UCl_5 complexes with nitrogen and oxygen donors^{2,3}. Solid reflectance spectra reported^{2,3} were recorded in a limited range because of the sensitivity of the complexes to moisture and lack of adequate arrangements to record spectra in an inert atmosphere. Therefore it could not be proved conclusively that there was no disproportionation of U(V) into U(IV) and U(VI). In fact disproportionation occurred to a significant extent during all the spectral measurements. The only peak corresponding to the $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_6$ transition (840-870 nm) was recorded. The absorption bands due to $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$, $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_7'$ and $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8'$ transitions had not been studied due to the non-availability of spectrophotometer with the required range at that time. In the present investigations UCl_5 complexes have been prepared in the dry box under dry nitrogen from UCl_5 solution in $SOCl_2$ and base solution in $SOCl_2$ as reported^{2,3}. Solid reflectance spectra of the complexes (600-2100 nm) were recorded using Beckman DK-2A Spectrophotometer (Fig. 1). The complexes were

Fig. 1. (A) $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ pyridine, (B) $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ quinoline, (C) $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ isoquinoline, (D) $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ benzil, (E) $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ anthrone.

well powdered, sealed by silicone high vacuum grease between the requisite plates in the dry box in dry nitrogen for recording their spectra.